

Citation for the Presentation of the 2020

ICPE Medal to

Dr. Roberto Nardi

At the IUPAP International Conference on Physics Education 2022

Professor Roberto Nardi is awarded the ICPE Medal for 2020 in recognition of his sustained and multifaceted contributions to Physics Education. He is completing fifty-three years of flourishing academic career and is known for his work in Physics Education, with significant contributions in Brazil, Latin America and beyond. His education began with obtaining his undergraduate Physics degree from São Paulo State University (UNESP) in Brazil in 1972. He completed his Master's Degree in Science Education from Temple University in Philadelphia (US) followed by his PhD in Science Education at the University of San Paulo (Brazil) in 1989, and he completed his postdoctoral training at Campinas State University (UNICAMP) from 2003 to 2004. His professional career also includes working as a physics teacher at high school after obtaining specialization in Physics Teaching in 1973.

Dr. Nardi obtained his Professorship Degree in 2005, from the University of São Paulo (UNESP) and became Professor, Vice- Chair and, finally, Chair of the Physics Department of State University of Londrina (UEL). Dr. Nardi has been working in the field of physics teachers' education at São Paulo State University (UNESP) since 1994, where, in 1997 he founded one of the first Science Education Graduate Programs in Brazil (and, in fact, entire Latin America). Today, this Program, 25 years later, is responsible for more than 650 master's and PhD graduates working across Brazil and in many countries around the world, such as: Colombia, Mexico, Canada and China. In the period between 1997 and 2022 Professor Nardi supervised more than one hundred students: among them, 22 Master's, 28 PhD, 8 Postdoctoral level, and numerous undergraduate students in research initiation placements. Many of them are today working and holding key positions in many universities across Brazil and abroad.

Dr. Nardi also participated in about 450 events on Physics and Science Teaching in Brazil and many other countries, not only as a presenter, but most often also as an organizer, or a member of scientific committees. These activities brought together researchers, teachers from various levels of

education, and students thus contributing to the growth and community recognition of the field of Physics Education Research (PER).

Throughout his career Dr. Nardi has made important contributions to the dissemination of scientific knowledge and collaboration between researchers, with the publication of 45 books, the creation of specialized journals, and editing Science Education journals, such as the Revista Ciência & Educação which he created in 1995, and where he is currently the lead editor. This is one of the first and most important Science Education journal in Ibero-America and abroad and has been a model for other journals mainly in Latin America.

Prof. Nardi holds a research productivity fellowship from the Brazilian National Research Council, with the highest rank (1A). He was the coordinator and member of the evaluation board of the Science and Mathematics Education Area (2008 to 2011) and member of the Technical Advisory Board (2008 to 2010) responsible for evaluation, training, and certification of in-service educators (CAPES).

His service includes being Secretary and President of the Physics Education Commission of the Brazilian Society of Physicists, and President of Brazilian Association of Science Education Research.

Internationally, Dr. Nardi served as a member of the Commission of Interamerican Conferences in Physics Education.

Finally, he chaired the C14 – Physics Education Commission of the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics (IUPAP) for 2017-2021 term of the Commission.

For his wide-ranging contributions, ICPE is happy to present the 2020 Medal to Professor Roberto Nardi.

Tetyana Antimirova

ICPE Chair